

RELATIONSHIP ANALYSIS BETWEEN QUALITY OF WORK LIFE (QWL) AND LABOURS ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT (LOC): A STUDY OF LARGE SCALE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES OF PUNE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Quality of Work Life and Labours Organizational Commitment serve as a foundation for all commercial operations inside the company and hence the researcher has considered the Quality of Work Life and Labours Organizational Commitment being the most essential reason for which this research is being conducted. The objective of the present study was to find the relationship between Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC) of the large-scale manufacturing industries of Pune district. Data were collected from 390 respondents. Three independent structured close ended schedules were used as instruments for collecting primary data from respondents. Simple Linear Regression & Multiple Linear Regression was used to find the impact of Quality of Work Life and Labours Organizational Commitment. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) test was used for analysis of relationship.

Keywords: *Quality of Work Life, Labours Organizational Commitment and large-scale manufacturing industries.*

Introduction

Employees are the organization's most valuable resource and its core strength. Organizations frequently place a greater emphasis on technology and systems than on personnel. It is not well recognised that employees are the ones who drive an organization's technologies and systems. Employees are not individuals working in the organisation; they are social creatures who belong to a specific social structure, family life style, and culture. The relevance of "Quality of Work Life" (QWL) in an organisation is not effectively taken care of due to a lack of knowledge among employers and employees. Absence of QWL results in job discontent, greater absenteeism, a lack of motivation and morale, higher accident rates, and worse productivity, among other things. These are the primary causes of an organization's poor performance, outnumbering all other factors. In organisations, QWL is critical to the proper operation of the business. It also aids in

attracting and maintaining efficient and productive people for the appropriate job profile, which leads to the success of both employees and companies. To ensure that all employees are working at their maximum ability while remaining stress-free, the Work-Life Balance must be carefully maintained. Employee dedication can come in a variety of shapes and sizes. As a result, it's frequently regarded as a difficult-to-define HR variable. When it comes to the context, direction, and growth of commitment, as well as the extent to which commitment drives behaviour, there can be confusion and debate. The bond that employees have with their organisation defines their devotion to it. Employees who are committed to their company have a sense of belonging, a sense of knowledge of the company's goals, and a sense of belonging in general. Because they are more engaged to their work, more productive, and more aggressive in delivering aid, such employees have a higher added value. Employee commitment is critical because high levels of

commitment result in a number of positive organisational outcomes. It demonstrates how dedicated employees are to the organization's aims and how much they identify with it. In today's competitive business world, every company faces the challenge of attracting and maintaining qualified employees. To counteract this, all firms must maintain a high level of Workplace Quality of Life. According to the literature, QWL is a movement that is a continuous process that has an impact on employee performance. Employee morale, commitment, efficiency, and effectiveness all suffer when the level of QWL falls. As a result, when developing QWL for employees, companies must consider issues like as morale, employee dedication, and so on. Every employee's Quality of Work Life (QWL) should be enjoyable; else, that individual would feel uncomfortable and demotivated in the organisation. This type of setting, on the other hand, has a direct impact on job satisfaction, performance, and productivity, as well as their general contentment at work. It can be concluded from the preceding analysis that there is a strong correlation between "Quality of Work Life" (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC). Thus, QWL is no longer just for show; it has become a necessity for employers, as its implementation has resulted in attracting better employees and lowering turnover, as well as enhanced job satisfaction, retention, devotion, loyalty, attention, and performance.

Quality of Work Life (QWL):

The concept "Quality of Work Life" first appeared in study journals and the press in the United States in the 1970s. The term "quality of work life" was coined by Louis Davis. The inaugural International Quality of Work Life Conference was held in Toronto in 1972, and

the next year, the International Council for "Quality of Work Life" was established.ⁱ

The basic concept of QWL is moved around its eight criteria of employment i.e. characteristics of the individual's work experience or work environmentⁱⁱ. Richard E. Walton QWL is explained in terms of eight general conditions which consist of "Adequate and fair compensation", "Safe and healthy working conditions", "Opportunity to use and develop human capacities", "Opportunity for continued career growth and security", "Social integration in work place", "Constitutionalism in the work organization", "Balanced role of work in total life space" and "Social relevance of work"ⁱⁱⁱ.

Organizational Commitment (OC):

Organisational commitment is describe in a variety of ways throughout the last few years (e.g. Meyer & Allen, 1991; J. P. Meyer, D. J. Stanley, L. Herscovitch, L. Topolnytsky, 2002, I. R. Gellatly, J. P. Meyer, A. A. Luchak, 2006, Mowday et al., 1979). Organisational commitment is thus made up of the following three components:

- 1) "one's strong belief in and acceptance of the organisation's goals and values",
- 2) "one's willingness to make considerable effort on behalf of the organisation",
- 3) "one's strong desire to maintain membership in the organisation".

The following are major aspects of organisational commitment:

1. **Affective commitment:** "refers to the employee's positive emotional attachment to the organization. The affective component means emotional commitment of an employee to the organization and identification with it. The persons with strong affective commitment continue their employment in the organization because they want to do so. The choice of the notion – affective commitment –

was conditioned by a belief that all factors involved in the development of this component are accompanied by strong positive feeling, and this is probably the most essential aspect of this form of commitment”^{iv}.

2. **Continuance commitment:** “refers to an employee’s commitment to an organization due to the fact that he calculates how high the costs of losing one’s organizational membership are. Such considerations might include economic costs (for instance, pension accruals) and social costs (relationships/friendships with colleagues might cease to exist) too”. Individuals feel that they “have to” commit to the organization. “The awareness of the costs associated with leaving the company is a component of the continuity component. Employees whose basic relationship to the company is based on the need to keep working there stay as long as they need to.”^v.
3. **Normative commitment:** “refers to an individual’s commitment an organization because of feelings of obligation. Such feelings might derive from the fact, for example, that the organization invested a certain amount of resources when employing the person (trainings, courses, etc.), which makes the employee feeling obliged to put considerable effort into the job and stay with the organization until repaying the debt. Furthermore, such feelings can also stem from personal reasons, triggered by some socialization processes, or one wishes to remain loyal to his family or any other person.” Therefore, the employee stays with the organization because he "ought to" do so. “These feelings arise out of a sense of duty or obligation. This particular component is affected largely by one’s personal experience, cultural

background, and socialization. There are cultures, for example, that of the Japanese, which are characterized by normative commitment, whereas affective commitment is typical of the Americans (János, 2005)”^{vi}.

The goal of this research was to find out more about large scale manufacturing companies of the Pune district. The existence of QWL programs in large scale manufacturing companies was essential in order to retain valuable employees as it also influenced their organizational commitment (OC). As a result, in order to establish the relationship between the two, “Quality of Work Life” (QWL) programs and “Labours Organizational Commitment” (LOC), the following questions is used:

Research Hypothesis:

H₀ : “There is no significant relationship between **Quality of Work Life (QWL)** and **Organizational Commitment (OC)**”.

H₁ : “There is significant relationship between **Quality of Work Life (QWL)** and **Labours Organizational Commitment (OC)**”.

Research Methodology

A. Research Design:

The present research is Diagnostic in nature as it is an in-depth study directed by hypotheses. Diagnostic inferential research design is used since, it focuses on relationship and association between variables such as QWL and OC. The Primary data has been collected in the form of feedback from sample blue collar labours to cogitate the impact of QWL on OC. Three independent structured close ended schedules were

used as instruments for collecting primary data from respondents.

B. Sample and Sampling Technique:

Labours working in the large-scale manufacturing industries of Pune district taken as samples. Simple random sampling method was used for sample selection since sample universe is large and researcher wants to obtain representative samples from each company. Samples of every company were approached in person to record the responses. There are 677 large scale manufacturing companies situated in Pune district out of which 114 companies were selected where the total employment is more than 500. The

sample universe of this research was 1,36,036. Researcher has used standard formula to calculate proposed sample size. Each company's samples added together to calculate actual sample size. The actual sample size of this research is **390 samples**.

C. Measurement:

The reliability analysis for final data of Schedule I, II & III was done by Cronbach's Alpha using of SPSS. Simple Linear Regression & Multiple Linear Regression has used to find the impact of impact of QWL on OC. Hypothesis was tested using Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) test has used to find out relationship between QWL & OC.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1.1. Demographic Distribution of Samples

(n=390)

Sr. No.	Demographic Variables	Gender			Total	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	Male		Female		
		Frequency	Frequency	%		%		
1	Marital Status	Single	39	18	57	10.0	4.6	14.6
		Married	274	59	333	70.3	15.1	85.4
		Separated	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Widowed	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Divorced	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Total	313	77	390	80.3	19.7	100.0
2	Education	Illiterate	-	-	-	-	-	-
		School: Up to 4 years	61	0	61	15.6	0	15.6
		School 5-9 years	54	0	54	13.8	0	13.8
		SSC	94	42	136	24.1	10.8	34.9
		HSC	13	21	34	3.3	5.4	8.7
		ITI	91	14	105	23.3	3.6	26.9
		UG	-	-	-	-	-	-
		PG	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Other	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	313	77	390	80.3	19.7	100.0		
3	Up to 5000	-	-	-	-	-	-	

	Income (Monthly)	6000 to 10,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
		11,000 to 15,000	20	0	20	5.1	0.0	5.1
		16,000 to 20,000	65	43	108	16.7	11.0	27.7
		Above 20,000	228	34	262	54.5	8.7	67.2
		Total	313	77	390	80.3	19.7	100.0
4	Employment Status	35-40 Hours Per Week	81	48	129	20.8	12.3	33.1
		41-45 Hours Per Week	2	12	14	0.5	3.1	3.6
		More than 45 Hours Per Week	230	17	247	59.0	4.4	63.3
		Any Other	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Total	313	77	390	80.3	19.7	100.0
5	Job Title/Occupation/ Designation	Carpenter	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Electrician	81	0	81	20.8	0.0	20.8
		Fitter	17	0	17	4.4	0.0	4.4
		Operator	72	0	72	18.5	0.0	18.5
		Gardening, Landscaping, etc	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Maintenance	53	0	53	13.6	0.0	13.6
		Line Leader	27	23	50	6.9	5.9	12.8
		Quality Checker	13	48	61	3.3	12.3	15.6
		Mechanical	8	0	8	2.1	0.0	2.1
		Painter	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Plumber	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Driver	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Welder	10	0	10	2.6	0.0	2.6
		Skilled Technician	16	0	16	4.1	0.0	4.1
		Packaging	16	6	22	4.1	1.5	5.6
Any other	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Total	313	77	390	80.3	19.7	100.0		

(Source: Field Data)

The impact of Quality of Work Life (QWL) factors on Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC)

Table 1.2.

Coefficients						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)		1.635	.084		19.446	.000
Adequate and fair compensation	X1	.053	.011	.136	4.788	.000
Safe and healthy environment	X2	.066	.009	.207	7.506	.000
Development of human capacities	X3	.116	.010	.271	11.331	.000
Growth and security	X4	.089	.009	.241	9.909	.000
Social integration	X5	.075	.009	.214	8.773	.000
Constitutionalism	X6	.081	.010	.224	8.480	.000
The total life space	X7	.070	.011	.190	6.660	.000
Social relevance	X8	.124	.014	.224	8.947	.000
Dependent Variable: Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC)						

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

In the above table a multiple regression calculated to predict Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC) based on Quality of Work Life (QWL) factors. Researcher has framed multiple regression equation to study the impact of eight Quality of Work Life factors (independent variable) on Labours Organizational Commitment (dependent variable).

$$\text{LOC} = 1.635 + 0.053 * X1 + 0.066 * X2 + 0.116 * X3 + 0.089 * X4 + 0.075 * X5 + 0.081 * X6 + 0.070 * X7 + 0.124 * X8$$

From above table it is clear that, Development of human capacities has more significant impact on Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC) with Beta value of 0.271 followed by Growth and security Social relevance & Constitutionalism with beta values 0.241, 0.224 & 0.224 respectively.

Fig: 1.1 The impact of Quality of Work Life (QWL) factors on Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC)

Table 1.3. The Correlation between Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC).

Correlations			
		QWL	LOC
QWL	Pearson Correlation	1	.948**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	390	390
LOC	Pearson Correlation	.948**	1

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	390	390
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

(Source: Compiled by Researcher)

Table No. 1.3 depicts the Pearson’s r states correlation between the Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC) which is 0.948. The Pearson’s r is 0.948 and this value is very much close to 1. However, it is revealed that there is a strong and positive relationship between Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC).

The Sig. (2-Tailed) value is 0.000. Thus ‘P’ value is 0.000 and this is less than 0.05 hence, null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis i.e. there is significant relationship between Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC) is accepted.

Graph 1.1

The above graph states trend line slopes upward from zero therefore; positive correlation between **Quality of Work Life (QWL)** and **Labours Organizational Commitment (LOC)**. Increases in first variable are correlated with increases in second variable. Also decreases in first variable are correlated with decreases in second variable.

Conclusion:

As the industrial sector becomes more essential to the economies of developed countries, organisations claim that their most precious asset is their personnel. Employees are more likely to report higher levels of performance and dedication if they believe a company provides them with high-quality work in exchange for their participation. Employees' sense of commitment will

improve if they have strong relationships and are cohesive in the company. QWL and OC are multidimensional constructs that are the result of a workplace examination. Employee commitment enables superior performance as well as greater attraction and retention of the best personnel, boosting the organization's ability to provide higher-quality services. Workplace satisfaction and organisational

commitment are linked. Workplace satisfaction has been found to have a major impact on organisational commitment. This suggests that employees who have a good quality of life at work are more devoted and have great commitment towards organization in all dimensions with their employers than those who have a bad quality of life at work.

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